

Advisory on UofG GenAI Assessment Scenarios

NOTE: Most links are only accessible by University of Glasgow staff as intended users of these resources.

Download the full advisory as PDF¹ or use this shorter check-list summar²y.

Purpose & Motivation

This set of recommendations aims to facilitate the effective implementation of the UofG Generative AI (GenAI) Assessment Scenarios [1]³, at both the undergraduate (UG) and postgraduate taught (PGT) levels within MVLS. The advisory is an initiative of the University of Glasgow (UofG) College for Medical, Veterinary and Life Sciences (MVLS) GenAI Intelligence Network for Education (GAINED) steering group in June 2025.

The UofG Learning and Teaching GenAI guidance [2]⁴ states that categorisation into one of the three GenAI Assessment Scenarios [1]⁵ is expected for all summative assessed work, and recommended for formative work, to ensure that both students and staff understand acceptable use of GenAI tools for different purposes. Students will expect communication about GenAI scenarios, which can be done in numerous ways, such as through assessment briefs or in-class discussion

Recommendations

RECOMMENDATION 1: Choose a single GenAI Assessment Scenario Per Assessment

The descriptions below expand upon the university guidance to showcase the role of GenAI scenarios within the broader course or programme. A single GenAI scenario should be chosen per item of assessment.

¹https://gla.sharepoint.com/:b:/s/MVLSGAINED-Steeringgroup/EQIIVBBy4mdFt5RqD7_3pQsBL8gqxzTxo--fHnwT6hC5Nw?e=CC4vUD

²<https://gla.sharepoint.com/:w:/s/MVLSGAINED-Steeringgroup/ETqmoUYc5I9GiTLRSYoplCMBsDG5guKib1LL3EtBAUGTFA?e=eSjUFa>

³<https://www.gla.ac.uk/myglasgow/learningandteaching/af-aiguideance/genaiassessmentscenarios/>

⁴<https://www.gla.ac.uk/myglasgow/learningandteaching/af-aiguideance/>

⁵<https://www.gla.ac.uk/myglasgow/learningandteaching/af-aiguideance/genaiassessmentscenarios/>

Scenario 1: Use of GenAI is fully permitted. Students are permitted to use any GenAI tool as long as it adheres to institutional policies, such as the UofG policies on GenAI use by students [3]⁶, by researchers [4]⁷, in academic misconduct [5]⁸, with third-party software [6]⁹ and copyright [7]¹⁰. This is appropriate where the assessment aligns with future professional settings or when independence is expected, because the decision resides with the student on whether and which GenAI tool to use in line with what is considered good practice in that discipline and institutional setting. It might be worth highlighting these policies or specific extracts thereof that are particularly relevant to the assessment.

Scenario 2: Use of GenAI tools is permitted with certain restrictions. This will likely apply to the majority of undergraduate assessments, especially complex tasks that are normally undertaken in the student's own time. The Integrity Statement will have specific guidance on which tasks may be undertaken with GenAI tools and to what extent. Scenario 2 can be used strategically across formative and summative tasks to focus on developing a particular skill. Restrictions can be designed to discourage over-reliance on GenAI tools or behaviours that undermine learning objectives and professional practice, whilst encouraging use that maximises learning opportunities.

Scenario 3: Non-use of GenAI. This scenario is used when the assessment aims to demonstrate individual acquisition of specific foundational knowledge or skills without external influence whilst undertaking the assessment. Realistically, adherence to scenario 3 can only be monitored through invigilation, making this the only category for a truly 'secure' assessment type. It likely does not accurately represent a real work environment [8]¹¹ but can be used strategically for quality assurance purposes, e.g. a threshold for progression [9]¹². Students may still use GenAI to prepare for the assessment and this can be signposted as resource, but this use of GenAI falls outside the scope of the directly evaluated component.

RECOMMENDATION 2: Balanced Approach

Avoid having all assessments in a course or programme fall solely under one scenario – aim for a balanced mix of all three scenarios as appropriate to the level of study. For example, GenAI scenario 3 can be reserved as strategic quality control checkpoint where it makes up at least 25% (but no more than 74%) of summative assessments for a course, year or programme, to make it a compulsory component if 75% completion is required for progression. We recommend the ratio between scenarios 1 and 2 change across the levels of study, with scenario 2 used as scaffolding in earlier years and the proportion of scenario 1

⁶<https://www.gla.ac.uk/myglasgow/sld/ai/students/>

⁷<https://www.gla.ac.uk/research/strategy/ourpolicies/ai-for-researchers/>

⁸<https://www.gla.ac.uk/myglasgow/studentconduct/academicmisconduct/>

⁹<https://www.gla.ac.uk/myglasgow/sld/digitalskills/thirdpartytools/#duediligencechecksandactivities>

¹⁰<https://www.gla.ac.uk/myglasgow/library/copyright/guidance/>

¹¹<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2412.09029>

¹²<https://educational-innovation.sydney.edu.au/teaching@sydney/what-to-do-about-assessments-if-we-cant-out-design-or-out-run-ai/>

increasing in advanced years as students work towards demonstrating more independence as expected in the workplace (see EXAMPLE 1). Alternating between scenarios 1 and 2 across linked formative and summative tasks can also maximise learning opportunities [8¹³, 9¹⁴, 10¹⁵], especially if implementing innovative teacher-approved GenAI tools.

We recommend tracking and reviewing GenAI scenarios across courses and programmes alongside the management of Assessment and Feedback Calendars.

EXAMPLE 1. The table demonstrates the shift in GenAI scenarios for assessments contributing to respective course grades across an undergraduate programme (not all courses shown). The proportion of GenAI scenario 1 increases from year 2 to year 4, whilst some components remain as scenario 3 (in person, with or without supplementary material).

	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
L2 optional course	-	40% (essay & lab report)	60% (class tests & exam)
L4 core skills course	10% (Moodle quizzes)	40% (Essay, annotated bibliography & reflective table for research rigour)	50% (Exam)
L4 Hons Project	80% (research project & supervisor mark)	-	20% (oral presentation)

1 - Click to expand Example 1

RECOMMENDATION 3: Use an Integrity Statement

We recommend having an Integrity Statement in place for each assessment that explicitly specifies its GenAI scenario and signpost to further support. Your school or college might have standardised statement text available for you to use and/or refer to. Integrate this Integrity Statement into the usual format in which assessment instructions are communicated to students (see EXAMPLE 2) so that it is not overlooked. Ensure the Integrity Statement is available in writing, easily accessible, disseminated to students before they start to engage with the assessment and there is opportunity for Q&A (specify contact details, offer anonymity or confidentiality, respond non-judgemental).

EXAMPLE 2. The Integrity Statement appears on the same page as instructions in the Assessment Information book on Moodle, which includes the course leader's email address for further inquiries. When introducing the assessment in class, it now also includes slides covering the Integrity Statement and the lecturer uses Mentimeter in class to answer anonymous questions.

2 - Click to expand Example 2

Try the GAINEd Tool¹⁶ to auto-draft an initial Integrity Statement.

See examples of full Integrity Statements¹⁷ for all three GenAI Scenarios for assessments associated with data analyses.

¹³<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2412.09029>

¹⁴<https://educational-innovation.sydney.edu.au/teaching@sydney/what-to-do-about-assessments-if-we-cant-out-design-or-out-run-ai/>

¹⁵<https://www.gla.ac.uk/myglasgow/learningandteaching/afresourceshub/whatislta/>

¹⁶https://forms.office.com/Pages/ResponsePage.aspx?id=KVxybjp2UE-B8i4ITwEzyLDogMkl_vJHpUQRi3dhdW1UME1HVVVZQ0s3R0NRUIhUVTdLS09BMUNaWC4u

¹⁷<https://sway.cloud.microsoft/tBSIb77dISnR1ZNo?ref=Link>

RECOMMENDATION 4: Connect to Learning Objectives

An optional recommendation is to use the Integrity Statement to justify the choice of GenAI scenario against the learning objective, which helps to understand how GenAI should not be used to complete the task on the student's behalf [11¹⁸]. GenAI literacy can improve when clarifying what GenAI-use is considered good and poor practice, in addition to misconduct, within the context of that assignment and outlining the associated consequences (e.g. lower grade or suspected misconduct process, see EXAMPLE 3). Expand upon university student guidance rather than repeating it.

EXAMPLE 3. A 400-word written literature research task that contains large portions of quoted text with in-text citations would not be seen as misconduct but it would be poor practice and lead to a low grade. Similarly, if a GenAI-powered tool was the *only* resource used in the same task to gather evidence from literature and the tool was appropriately credited, this would be poor research practice but not constitute misconduct. Whether the student's approach affects the grade will depend on the assessment design and marker training. Whether a student *knows* that this approach would be inappropriate for this task will depend on the Integrity Statement or other support provision.

3 - Click to expand Example 3

We recommend breaking down the assessment into anticipated tasks, using it to guide students through the potential role of GenAI (and other resources) for each (see EXAMPLE 4). This approach simplifies decisions on GenAI use while providing clear restrictions for each task. Set reasonable expectations aligned with learning objectives and the university's accessibility policy, rather than trying to use the Integrity Statement to make the assessment 'GenAI-proof'.

MVLS GAINEd developed a skills mapping resource¹⁹ to help staff and students across different programmes to be more consistent in guidance around what sort of GenAI-use would be considered responsible versus risky. The skills mapping resource also suggests assessment types that could be employed for more direct evaluation of that particular skill.

¹⁸<https://www.gla.ac.uk/myglasgow/apg/policies/uniregs/regulations2023-24/feesandgeneral/studentssupportandconductmatters/reg32/>

¹⁹https://gla.sharepoint.com/:b/s/MVLSGAINEd/Efxfu5oflbVII1PODGv_JrcBeZvUa3E9LqNTO-vdwzMpfA?e=3sHz89

EXAMPLE 4. The table lists a breakdown of tasks associated with preparing a literature review essay and contains detailed descriptions because it is meant to support earlier years of study. The assessment as a whole is categorised as GenAI scenario 2, but for each task the same 3 principles are applied: yes, maybe (with caution), or no (with justification). Not adhering to this Integrity Statement is considered GenAI misuse.

Activity Name	Description of your actions (who/what/when & how)	Okay to use GenAI tools?
Brainstorming and consultation to broaden understanding	Early-stage preparation can include general reading, online searches, consulting blogs, textbooks, or GenAI tools, as well as discussing ideas with peers or support services. These activities help expand your understanding, shape your perspective, and refine your research focus. Use them to guide your thinking—not to do the work for you—and always credit any significant input (e.g. in an acknowledgements section). Remember to distinguish this exploratory phase from the formal process of gathering reliable, evidence-based sources for your essay.	Yes
Scientific review of the literature	This is the scientific approach of seeking evidence to objectively investigate a topic. It is a process by which you make use of reliable databases and research tools alongside effective search criteria to find and critically select appropriate sources to substantiate any claims you make and strengthen your arguments. This process represents the scientific rigour of your work, no matter which audience it is aimed at. Your scientific rigour will increase as you rely more heavily upon scientific databases and peer-reviewed sources, critically integrating information across multiple such sources.	Yes, but not on its own as otherwise it is not done with sufficient scientific rigour. Use in conjunction with traditional methods.
Managing References and Citations	The effectiveness of your literature investigation will greatly improve by keeping a record of your process. Develop strategies to keep track of the details for your database searches, source selection and which information came from which source. Consider using tools or methods to organise and keep a record of your references, including correct formatting of your final reference list and in-text citations.	Yes, but requires critical review
Drafting	This is the process by which you put together evidence from selected sources into logical arguments. Consider strategies to keep track of what information comes from where so that you give appropriate credit to the source(s) and avoid possible plagiarism. This process of choosing what goes into your draft should be done by you and not by anybody else. By the end of the drafting process, you should have a collection of information from your selected sources.	No - it is essential you do this yourself to meet the learning objectives for this assessment
Structuring, editing and proofreading	Once you drafted your information, you can evaluate whether any improvements can be made in how the information flows throughout, whether your wording can be more concise or clear in its meaning, and correct any spelling and grammar issues. Try to do this as best as you can before consulting other people, services or tools. Review any suggested changes carefully before approving it to avoid issues such as a shift in your original meaning or in-text citations leading to wrongful attribution. Double-check formatting of references and in-text citations. Include an acknowledgements section to give credit to any people/tools/services that contributed to the work.	Yes, but requires critical review

4 - Click to expand Example 4

RECOMMENDATION 5: Acknowledging GenAI Tools

Follow the UofG GenAI guidance for students and researchers on how to credit GenAI, e.g. either as personal communication or specifying its contribution in an acknowledgement section. In the Integrity Statement, explicitly state how students are expected to credit GenAI in that specific context, e.g. format, word count implications, level of detail. See EXAMPLE 5.

EXAMPLE 5. A lecturer wants to encourage students to acknowledge if/how they used GenAI in a written task.

Option 1: Require a 100-word reflection on GenAI tool usage.

- **Not Useful:** If increasing workload for GenAI users.
- **Useful:** If graded or penalized for omission. Include all students by asking to reflect on all resources used, including GenAI and non-GenAI. Should provide support and grading criteria.

Option 2: Declaration (e.g. in Moodle or insert into submitted work).

- **Not Useful:** If asking for Yes/No on GenAI usage – the ‘how’ it was used is more meaningful.
- **Useful:** Accepting a declaration of understanding and upholding the Integrity Statement associated with that assessment. Need to specify this requirement as part of assessment instructions before they start working on it.

Option 3: Acknowledgements section.

- **Not Useful:** Students may omit it. Make it compulsory and provide guidance in the Integrity Statement/assessment instructions, including word count implications.
- **Useful:** Thoughtful crediting of resources in line with good professional practice within that discipline/context.

5 - Click to expand Example 5

RECOMMENDATION 6: Evaluate and improve

We recommend getting peer feedback on newly developed Integrity Statements for scrutiny, such as through teaching teams, external examiner or via the MVLS GAINED Teams site²⁰.

²⁰https://teams.microsoft.com/l/team/19%3AY1E1OrUw9Q_W1Wz5BrtDxgK2NJuKDdvY9HC0nOvaU5o1%40thead.tacv2/conversations?groupId=93854c46-3a6f-4ad9-8429-38a0f3070860&tenantId=6e725c29-763a-4f50-81f2-2e254f0133c8

Gather student feedback on Integrity Statements, discuss its effectiveness at teaching meetings or board of examiners and continue to make appropriate adjustments.

RECOMMENDATION 7: Marking process

We recommend disseminating the Integrity Statement to markers. Discuss how GenAI use may manifest in student work and agree appropriate actions, such as flagging concerns and providing consistent feedback. Ensure markers remain unbiased, encourage open dialogue, and use the MVLS GAINEd community to raise or share insights. Provide positive feedback to students where GenAI is used well to reinforce good practices. If GenAI use is apparent but not credited, or if GenAI use is suspected to be in breach of the Integrity Statement, flag the case appropriately for suspected misconduct [5²¹, 11²²]. Where GenAI is used poorly but not in breach of guidance (e.g. citing it for facts), offer constructive feedback that explain concerns, signpost support, and offer follow-up discussion if needed. See EXAMPLE 6.

EXAMPLE 6. The following statement is included as feedback to a 2nd year student after submitting their first written work for this course. The marker flagged that it looks like GenAI was used, but there is no acknowledgement of using a GenAI tool. The course leader cannot see any valid evidence to take forward as misconduct, but wants to encourage good practice, therefore includes this statement. "As outlined in the assessment instructions' Integrity Statement, you are allowed to use generative AI tools to help with structuring, editing and proof-reading of your work that you drafted yourself. There appears to be evidence of this in your work, which may or may not be true, but it is important to realise that if you use of any form of AI without acknowledging that input, it counts as academic misconduct. We provide this feedback because we want to support you in learning how to use these tools effectively, ethically, critically, and transparently in future studies. Support is provided in this course's Good Practice in Research lab, and you are very welcome to contact your course leader to discuss."

6 - Click to expand Example 6

Acknowledgements

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Feedback

We welcome any feedback on this advisory via this Form²³.

²¹<https://www.gla.ac.uk/myglasgow/studentconduct/academicmisconduct/>

²²<https://www.gla.ac.uk/myglasgow/apg/policies/uniregs/regulations2023-24/feesandgeneral/studentssupportandconductmatters/reg32/>

²³<https://forms.office.com/Pages/ResponsePage.aspx?id=KVxybjp2UE-B8i4ITwEzyHXNWlz1HMVOhmellvZFwDtUOUQ1UVpEWINZNIIBVUZYMdRaUFY4MTRGTi4u>

We invite you to share your Integrity Statement or other examples of GenAI-related good practice via this Form²⁴. GAINEd is always looking for ways to share good practice and learn from combined efforts.

References

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²⁴<https://forms.office.com/Pages/ResponsePage.aspx?id=KVxybjp2UE-B8i4ITwEzyHXNWlz1HMVOhmellvZFwDtUNkdRMjczM0RUUUlPMVVTMUNDQ1pMQlhSQi4u>

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10. University of Glasgow (2023) *Learning Through Assessment Framework*. Available from:
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Advisory Checklist

- (required) Each summative assessment is categorised under a single GenAI Assessment Scenario
- The GenAI Scenario is justified against the learning objectives
- The GenAI Scenario was considered in context of the broader course or programme
- Considered the GenAI Scenario and assessment design in line with the university's policies on accessibility and inclusion
- The GenAI Scenario is explicitly stated as part of the assessment instructions
- Identified how an Integrity Statement will be disseminated to students (available in writing, accessible format, disseminated beforehand)
- The Integrity Statement includes signposting to relevant institutional policies (e.g. academic misconduct, GenAI guidance for students/researchers, third-party software, copyright)
- Integrity Statement includes consequences of not adhering to the guidance, clarifying what is considered misconduct or poor versus good practice
- Integrity Statement includes instruction on how/where to credit GenAI
- (optional) Integrity Statement includes a breakdown of anticipated assessment tasks, indicating how GenAI use may be appropriate or not for each

- (optional) Integrity Statement lists teacher-approved GenAI resources and/or non-GenAI alternatives
- Integrity Statement includes communication method for student Q&A
- Marker training disseminates GenAI Scenario and Integrity Statement with opportunity for Q&A
- Markers understand what to flag for suspected misconduct or how to provide constructive feedback for poor and good practice related to GenAI
- Assessment coordinator understands how to review flagged cases of suspected GenAI misuse, and how to either follow misconduct procedures or provide constructive feedback
- (optional) Engage with the MVLS GAINEd network to get peer support on Integrity Statements, share experiences, raise concerns, and develop best practices collaboratively
- Gather student and marker feedback on GenAI communications for assessment